

Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through
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Digital Marketing a Boost for Industries:
A Study with Respect to Miraj Taluka

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ABSTRACT

Today, digital marketing is of foremost importance to any business, industries as digital presence has become an essential necessity to make their presence. The world is now moving from old newspaper advertisements to new handy Smartphone advertisements and so is India. The old days are gone when industries would rely on distributing surveys to collect information about the market. Data analyses, data gathering are the trending ways for a business to do its market research. The biggest problem in India's digital marketing scenario, primarily in tier 2 and tier 3 cities like Sangli, Miraj is poor internet infrastructure and technology adoption. But this scenario is changing rapidly because India is modernizing at a very fast pace and internet is a necessity as food, shelter and clothing. Hence tier 3 cities are also gradually evolving to be tech-friendly and therefore businesses should start pacing their strategies accordingly soon!

KEYWORDS: Tier 3 cities, Digital Marketing, Marketing Strategies

I. INTRODUCTION

The internet has unlocked the door of enormous digital marketing opportunities for businesses today. Digital marketing is the marketing of your products or services using digital technologies like website, apps, search engines, emails and social media, mainly on the Internet. The main objective of Digital marketing is to increase brand loyalty, brand awareness and to reach the customers in personal, relevant, timely and cost effective manner. The traditional ways of marketing involved industries to advertise their services or products on print media, radio and television commercials, business cards, Hoardings, banners and many other ways where online medium were not utilize for advertising. But now businesses are investing more in digital marketing for growing fast and gaining profitable results. Digital marketing gives industries of any size access to the mass market at an reasonable and cheaper price unlike print or TV advertising, it allows truly real time and personalized marketing. Digital marketing is involving in everything that goes on in the company from the marketing end today. Therefore it is very important to have a strong online presence for business.

India has emerged as the fast paced growing economy in the world as per the Central Statistics Organization and the International Monetary Fund. In India 35 percent of the population is using the Internet today, and by 2025, this figure is about to reach 55 percent or more. Today the average age of an Internet user in India is 24 years old or younger, it means that only a minority of the working people in India use the Internet for business on a daily basis, which leads to a conclusion that the Golden Age of digital marketing in India is yet to come. The main key players in Digital

marketing in India are the Government, Shopping Portal, banking system, Software Service Providers and Internet Service Providers. The telecommunication sector is also performing a crucial role in the digitalization of India. Especially the reliance telecom Jio has played a revolutionary roll by providing the free & unlimited internet facilities. People are spending most of their times on internet compared to previous years. So being present on the online medium is a necessity of businesses, which will help for more growth and opportunities.

In India, there are some challenges which digital marketers are facing. There are two main ones that are common for both in-house marketers and agency. One is budget, which nobody seems to have in India. The second and more important one is lack of awareness. The lack of awareness is playing major role while creating digital marketing strategies. This especially happens in Tier II and more in Tier III cities. Tier I cities, which include the metropolises and the highly developed industrial and cultural hubs and the Tier II and Tier III cities which include the developing regions around the country. India is the second largest user of cell phones and the increasing number of mobile users also contributes to the enlarging digital consumer base. Therefore the telecom companies like Jio, BSNL, Idea, Vodafone etc. have introduced mega saving offers on their services and mobile handsets to successfully capture into the untapped market of Tier II and Tier III cities. These Tier II and Tier III cities consist of a major part of the Indian population, which can come up with great opportunity pool, making it an attractive market for business. It is also a reality that the large scale application of digital technologies in Tier I city has brought in a saturation that's why leading investors to shift focus to the lower tiers.

Digital marketing techniques includes Website, Search Engine Marketing(SEM), Search Engine Optimization(SEO), Social Media Marketing(SMM), Email Marketing, Content Marketing, Mobile Marketing, Blogging, Affiliate Marketing, SMS Marketing Remarketing and Analytics.

A. Website:

Company's online address is nothing but the website. Every business should have their user friendly responsive website to take advantage of Digital Marketing. The website must fulfils the essential things like responsiveness, user-friendliness, easy to navigate, loading time and consumer tracking tools.

B. Search Engine Marketing(SEM):

Search Engine Marketing manages the traffic whether it may be the organic or paid traffic through PPC. PPC means Pay-Per-Click. The Pay-Per-Click or paid marketing is one of the fastest method to rank high in the organic search results. There are various platforms for Search Engine Marketing like CPM (cost-per-thousand impressions) model or PPC (pay-per-click) or CPC (cost-per-click) model. Depending upon structure of business and strategies, businesses may choose those models.

C. Search Engine Optimization(SEO):

Search Engine Optimization is the technique for optimizing the content of a website to improve its ranking on the Search Engine Results Page. It is the reason you get the traffic or the viewers to your website. There are some well known search engines like Google, Yahoo, Bing, Baidu and Yandex. Optimizing the content in the website, having related keywords, building the back-links will help to increase the page traffic and a large number of viewers come to the website. Search engine optimization improves the organic search results.

D. Social Media Marketing (SMM):

Social Media Marketing is the process of promoting your brand and your content through social networking media

channels to build brand value, get the traffic, and generate leads to your business. Facebook, Youtube, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, Whatsapp, Pinterest, are well known social media platforms which can be utilized as a part of social media optimization. Social media Marketing involve both paid and unpaid marketing strategy. The aim is to engage substantial amount of people as possible and get larger the social engagement which can later to turned into the loyal customers. This is a significant digital marketing component which no businesses can never ignore.

E. Email Marketing:

Email marketing is for retargeting a customer and performing the rebranding of your company. It is the strategy of sending commercial messages through email to a list of prospects and potential customers. When people get the email, they think this is only for them and no one else gets this opportunity. Marketing through emails helps in targeting individual customer and making them know about your brand , your product and the latest things.

F. Content Marketing:

Content is the very important thing of online marketing. Content is king for any website and the digital media. A catchy and crispy content is liked and shared very rapidly. The creation of useful content is a method for commencing communication with the customer so as to drive engagement and customer activity. Businesses need to engage their customers on a daily basis by writing blogs, making videos and images, white-papers, presentations etc.

G. Affiliate Marketing:

Affiliate Marketing is a kind of performance based publicizing where you get commission for promoting another person's services or products on your website. In affiliate marketing, online retailer pays commission to an external website for sales or traffic generated from its referrals.

H. Remarketing:

Remarketing is also called as retargeting. It is a technique to target the customers who have already visited or taken action on your website. Remarketing helps the company better engagement with online customers. We can capture what are the interests of online customers which helps to engage these users.

I. Analytics:

Analytics is mainly concentrated on understanding the past, present and future; what happened, what is happening and what will happen. Web analytics is the process of knowing the behaviour of visitors to a website. The Web analytics is a way for measuring web traffic which can be used as a tool for market research, business strategies, decision making and to measure and improve the efficiency and performance of a website.

II. Digital Marketing Scenario In Industries Situated In Miraj Taluka

Miraj is a Taluka in Sangli District of Maharashtra State in India. Miraj town is the Head Quarter of Miraj Taluka. It belongs to west Maharashtra region under Pune Division and it is located. 359 KM from State capital Mumbai towards North. Marathi is the Local Language and people also speaks Kannada due to Karnataka boundary. There are 3 towns and

64 villages in Miraj taluka. The smallest Village in Miraj Taluka is Sambarwadi and Malgaon is the biggest Village. In Miraj Taluka, there are two MIDCs: Kupwad MIDC and Miraj MIDC. Sangli Miraj MIDC Industrial Area was set up in 1972. There are more than 500 companies are working in Sangli Miraj MIDC Industrial Area. This is one of the oldest Industrial Area in Sangli District. Sangli Miraj MIDC Manufacturers Association (SMMMA) and Krishna Valley Chamber Of Industries & Commerce (KVCIC) are the associations mainly established for to set up Common Communication Forum for Industries, to interact internally within members & put forward industries view points to various dimensions of Government & Key Regulatory Authority and press for pro-industry activities. SMMMA belongs to Miraj MIDC and KVCIC belongs to Kupwad MIDC. At present, in Sangli Miraj MIDC Manufacturers Association, 250 registered members and 318 registered members in the Krishna Valley Chamber Of Industries & Commerce. So the total unique registered industries are 568.

The Digital Marketing component like Social Media, Search Engine Optimization, Paid Campaigns, SMS marketing are well known in Miraj Taluka. In Social Media Facebook, Whatsapp and Instagram are more popular as compared to Twitter, LinkedIn etc. Local listing sites like indiamart, justdial are also very popular in industries in Miraj Taluka.

Chart no. 1 those who have Website

From the chart no.1 it shows that out of the total industries, 68% of the industries have their own website and remaining 32% of the industries do not have their own website. This indicates that majority of businesses having website of their company.

Chart no. 2 Those who have Google Business Listing

From the chart no.2 it shows that out of the total industries, 60% of the industries have listed their business in Google Business Listing and 40% of the industries have not their business in Google Business Listing.

Chart no. 3 Those who have presence on Social Media

From the chart no 3 it shows that out of the total industries, only 61% of the industries have created their Face book Business Page and 39% of the industries don't have their Face book Business Page. This indicates that less businesses having their Face book Business Page. 28% of the industries have Instagram Business Profile, only 11% of the industries Twitter account, 23% of the industries LinkedIn account and 16% of the industries have their YouTube channel. This indicates that Majority of businesses have their Face book profile as compared to other social media sites like Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube.

Chart no.4 Those who have presence on Local Listing Sites

From the chart no 4 it shows that out of the total industries, 85% of the industries have their presence on indiamart.com and 88% of the industries have their presence on justdial.com. This indicates that very less businesses who don't have their presence on indiamart.com and justdial.com.

III. Conclusion

As per the data collected it is seen that the industries situated in Miraj Taluka are not using entire Digital Marketing. There are many important components and tools of Digital Marketing like website, search engine optimization(SEO),search engine marketing(SEM), social media, content marketing, mobile marketing, email marketing, affiliate marketing, remarketing, blogging, web analytics, online reputation management, app store optimization but very less tools are being used in industries in Miraj Taluka. So we can say that there is lack of awareness of digital Marketing in industries. Industries here, have more presence on local listing sites like Just dial and India mart. Digital marketing is very cost effective as compared to traditional and having a very good commercial impact on the business. The customers are looking and searching more on digital medium to find the best deals and offers from the market. So Businesses must have their presence in all digital media. So there are excellent opportunities for industries situated in Miraj Taluka to spread their business using digital medium.

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